

Possible Psychopharmacological Agents. Part XII—Synthesis and CNS Activity of Some Fluorine Containing 2-Oxo-1-phenylpyrazolo[1,5-a]Pyrimidines

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New fluorine containing 5,7-disubstituted-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-1-phenylpyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines have been synthesized by the condensation of 3-amino-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone with fluorinated 1,3-diketones in acetic acid and characterized by ir, pmr and ^{19}F nmr spectral studies. CNS activity of some representative compounds has also been evaluated and three compounds exhibited significant antiinflammatory activity. Analgesic and anticonvulsant activities were not found at dose levels of 200 and 112 mg/kg.

KEEPING in view the observation of Ratajczyk *et al*¹ who reported anticonvulsant, sedative, antiinflammatory, gastric antisecretory and central nervous system activities of 1,3-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-7-one and as part of a comprehensive programme of developing new biologically active fluorine containing heterocycles as psychopharmacological agents, ten 5,7-disubstituted-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-1-phenylpyrazolo[1,5-a]-pyrimidine derivatives have been synthesized and screened for their CNS activity. The synthesis involved the condensation of 3-amino-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone with appropriate fluorinated 1,3-diketones in acetic acid² (Scheme-I).

(Scheme I)

Experimental

Melting points of all synthesized compounds are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer (Model-337) in KBr mull. PMR and ^{19}F nmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer (Model-RB12). TMS was taken as internal standard for

pmr and TFA was taken as external standard for ^{19}F nmr spectra. TFA was used as solvent for pmr and ^{19}F nmr spectra.

3-Amino-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone : It was prepared by the condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate (0.1 mole, 11.3 g) with phenylhydrazine (0.1 mole, 10.8 g) in the presence of sodium ethylate; m.p. 219° (Lit.³ m.p. 218-200°), yield 9.0 g, 51%.

1,3-Dione derivatives : 1-(4-Fluorophenyl) butane-1,3-dione⁴ ; 4,4,4-trifluoro-1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione⁵ ; 4,4,4-trifluoro-1-(4-fluorophenyl) butane-1,3-dione⁶ ; 1-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione⁴ ; 1-(3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl) butane-1,3-dione⁶ ; 4,4,4-trifluoro-1-(3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl) butane-1,3-dione⁶ ; 4,4,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl)pentane-1,3-dione⁶ ; 1-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl) butane-1,3-dione⁴ ; 4,4,4-trifluoro-1-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl) butane-1,3-dione⁴ ; 1-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione⁴ derivatives were prepared by the condensation of the appropriate fluorinated acetophenone (0.1 mole) with a suitable ester (0.2 mole) in presence of sodium amide (0.2 mole) in dry solvent ether.

5,7-Disubstituted-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-1-phenylpyrazolo [1,5-a]pyrimidine : Equimolar quantities of 3-amino-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (0.1 mole) and fluorinated 1,3-diones (0.1 mole) were heated for 10 min in glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was kept as such for 48 hr after which the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residual solid recrystallized from ethanol/methanol. Details of amounts of different reactants taken, yields, m.ps. and physical data are given in Table 1.

Spectral characterization : Strong absorption at 3200-3350 cm^{-1} and 1640 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of 3-amino-5-pyrazolone confirms the presence of $-\text{NH}_2$ and $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups. New peaks appear at

TABLE 1—5,7-DISUBSTITUTED-1,2-DIHYDRO-2-OXO-1-PHENYLPYRAZOLO[1,5-a]PYRIMIDINES

Sl. No.	3-amino-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (in g)	1,3-dione (in g)	Yield (%)	m.p. °C	R	R'	Molecular formula	Analysis Calcd.N(%)	Found N(%)
1.	1.7	2.1	80	190	CF ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ F ₃ N ₂ O	11.93	11.64
2.	1.7	1.8	75	200	CH ₃	4-F,C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O	13.16	13.08
3.	1.7	2.3	88	217	OF ₂	4-F,C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₂ O	11.26	11.10
4.	1.7	2.4	65	135	C ₆ H ₅	4-F,C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ FN ₂ O	11.02	10.95
5.	1.7	2.1	69	240	CH ₃	3-F,4-OCH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ FN ₂ O ₂	12.03	11.89
6.	1.7	2.6	78	160	OF ₂	3-F,4-OCH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.42	10.31
7.	1.7	3.2	83	168	C ₂ F ₅	3-F,4-OCH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂	9.27	9.09
8.	1.7	2.1	65	115	OH	3-Cl,4F,C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ClFN ₂ O	11.88	11.68
9.	1.7	2.6	78	135	OF ₂	3-Cl,4F,C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ ClF ₂ N ₂ O	10.30	10.19
10.	1.7	2.7	81	150	C ₆ H ₅	3-Cl,4F,C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClFN ₂ O	10.10	10.03

1665 cm⁻¹ in 2-oxo-1-phenylpyrazolo [1,5-a]pyrimidines due to >C=N and at 1140-1210 cm⁻¹ due to Ar-F stretching vibrations.

PMR spectrum showed signals in the region δ 0-1.5 ppm (3H, CH₃); δ 2.0-3.5 ppm (3H, OCH₃) and aromatic protons at δ 6.9-7.8 ppm. Positions of R and R' in 2-oxo-1-phenylpyrazolo [1,5-a]pyrimidines can be explained on the basis of the direction of enolization in 1,3-diones being towards phenyl ring⁶. In ¹⁹F nmr spectra, signals at δ 32-42 ppm indicate fluorinated aryl group and those at δ -10-5 ppm are due to -CF₃ group.

Evaluation of CNS activity in mice : Compounds number 3,5,6,8 and 9 in Table 1 have been screened for CNS activity on different parameters in mice. All the compounds were administered intraperitoneally (i.p.) as suspension in gum acacia.

Gross effects : The animals were observed for 2 hr after drug administration for any evidence of CNS stimulation or depression or any autonomic effect by the method of Dhar *et al*⁷. This involved noting the effect on (i) spontaneous motor activity, (ii) certain reflexes e.g. righting, corneal and pinnal, (iii) muscle tone (reduced and catalepsy), (iv) ataxia and writhing, (v) eyes (pupils and ptosis), (vi) respiration and (vii) observing them for the occurrence of tremor, convulsions, straub's tail, piloerection. At different dose levels, SMA, respiration and reactivity towards sound and touch decrease, writhing is present and animals become less active. Mortality is "nil" within 24 hr in compounds number 8 and 9. Compounds thus act as mild CNS depressant, approximate LD₅₀ is 562 mg/kg in compound number 6 and in case of all other compound greater than 1000 mg/kg.

Special tests : Analgesic (tail pinch method)⁸ and anticonvulsant (SMES test)⁹ activities were not found at a dose of 200 and 112 mg/kg.

Carrageenan induced edema was produced in albino rats. Compounds number 5, 6 and 9 exhibited significant antiinflammatory activity (14%, 18%, 20%) with indomethacin as a reference compound (inhibition is 40-50% at a dose level of 4 mg/kg approx.)

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References

1. J. D. RATAJCZYK, R. G. STEIN and L. R. SWETT, *U. S. Patent*, 3,939,161, 1976; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, 84, 164835m.
2. S. EL-ZANFALLY and S. EL-BASIL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16B, 496.
3. CONRAD and ZART, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2133.
4. K. C. JOSHI and V. N. PATHAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 435.
5. J. C. REID and M. CALVIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2943.
6. K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and S. BHARGAVA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, 39, 803.
7. M. L. DHAR, M. M. DHAR, B. N. DHAWAN, B. N. MEHROTRA and C. RAY, *Indian J. Expt. Biol.*, 1968, 6, 232.
8. C. BIANCHI and J. FRANCESCHINE, *Brit. J. Pharmacol. Chemotherap.*, 1954, 9, 280.
9. E. SWINYARD, *J. Amer. Pharm. Ass., Sci. Ed.*, 1949, 38, 201.